

“A STUDY ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF SWEET ORANGE FARMERS IN ANANTAPURAMU DISTRICT”

Arjun Reddy N. R.¹, Vijaychandra Reddy S.², V. Sitarambabu¹, K. N. Sreenivasulu³¹ Department of Agricultural Economics, Agricultural College, Bapatla, Acharya NG Ranga Agricultural University (ANGRAU)² Department of Agricultural Economics, University of Agricultural Sciences, Raichur³ Department of Statistics and Computer Applications, Agricultural College, Bapatla, Acharya NG Ranga Agricultural University (ANGRAU)vijaychandraphd@gmail.com

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Abstract

In Andhra Pradesh, Anantapuramu district has the highest area of 0.611 lakh ha and production of 14.67 lakh tonnes under sweet oranges. (Agricultural statistics at a glance, Andhra Pradesh, 2020-21). Multistage purposive sampling technique was employed for selection of farmers during the year 2020-21. From each village 7 participants and 13 non-participants were selected. A total of 63 participants and 117 non-participants participating in retail marketing were selected. The finding on socio-economic status reveals that, majority of the participants were less than ten years' experience (69.84 per cent). Farmers with experience greater than twenty years were majorly non-participants (30.77 per cent). The findings on annual income shows that, Majority of the non-participants belonged to the income range less than 5.5 lakhs (36.75 per cent) followed by income range 5.5 to 6 lakhs (29.91 per cent), 6 to 6.5 lakh (28.21 per cent) and 6.5 to 7 lakh (5.13 per cent). Farmers participating in retail marketing were getting higher level of income compared to non-participant respondents.

Key words: Retail marketing, Socio-Economic Status, Oranges, participation.

Introduction

Indian agriculture is dominated by innumerable small and marginal farms which are highly dispersed and unorganized. Further, the agricultural goods are extremely perishable in nature and its supply is also erratic owing to seasonality and both biotic and abiotic stresses, these calls for appropriate management of supply chains that can address the emerging issues and facilitates higher value especially in retail markets in India.

Due to the introduction of numerous fresh enterprises, the Indian retail industry has become one of the country's most vibrant and quick-paced sectors. It contributes to over ten percent of the nation's GDP (Gross Domestic Product) and about eight percent of employment. India ranks as the fifth most popular retail destination in the world, with one of the highest rates of retail store accessibility per inhabitant (Kartheka *et al.*, 2019). On the contrary, despite the robust demand and increasing investment in Indian retail market, it was purely due to production of agricultural commodities especially fruits and vegetables.

Sweet orange is an important crop in the Far East, the Union of South Africa, Australia, throughout the Mediterranean area, subtropical areas of South America and the Caribbean. It is produced in many countries around the world especially in warm and tropical weathers. Sweet orange contains large amounts of potassium, which might help to prevent high blood pressure and stroke. The fruit and juice also contain large amounts of a chemical called citrate, which might help to prevent kidney stones. Due to the significance of sweet oranges in human diet, there is a high demand for them in the market. In this background sweet oranges were selected for the current study.

Sweet orange has a world production of 750 lakh tonnes for the year 2020. India stands at second position after Brazil, followed by China and the United States. (FAOSTAT, 2020). India has a production of 38.94 lakh tonnes of sweet orange. Andhra Pradesh is the leading producer of sweet orange in India with production of 27 lakh tonnes and area of 1.12 lakh ha. (MoA and FW, 2022). In Andhra Pradesh, Anantapuramu district has the highest area of 0.611 lakh ha and production of 14.67 lakh tonnes under sweet oranges. (Agricultural statistics at a glance, Andhra Pradesh, 2020-21). The supply chain is critical in the marketing of perishable foods like fruits. Fruit marketing is difficult due to perishability, seasonality, bulkiness, and consumer buying habits. Furthermore, in the current context, the infrastructure, poor supply chain equity, and traditional small-scale unorganised retailers. The vast majority of the Indian retail market is dominated by unorganised retailers. The recent development in the retailing industry is the emergence of numerous organised retailers. Socio-economic status (SES) is a collective dimension for the measurement of economic and social situation of an entity compared

to others section of the society. It influences the accessibility to the both off farm and on farm resources, pattern of livelihood, basic level of nutritional & food security based on Income earning and land holding. It often predicts the psychological and behavioural components of a sample viz. attitude, knowledge, adoption, perception, risk bearing ability, economic motivation etc. Present study tried to investigate SES.

The socio-economic pattern of farmers can be improved if they enjoy market linkages with retail markets. Further, in view of the perishability of the produce these market linkages help in timely transaction of produce. Therefore, it is essential to find the socio-economic status of the farmers to supply sweet orange in retail market. So, the study focused on “socio-economic status of sample farmers for supply in retail markets by sweet orange farmers in Anantapuramu district” was conducted, with the following objective To study the socio-economic status of sample respondents for supply in retail markets by sweet orange farmers in Anantapuramu district.

Materials and Methods

Multistage purposive sampling technique was followed for selection of state, district, mandals and villages, thereafter random sampling was employed for selection of farmers. In India, Andhra Pradesh state was selected for the study as it has the highest area of 0.87 lakh ha and production of 18.78 lakh tonnes of sweet oranges by considering average of past seven years data. (Agricultural Statistics at a Glance, Andhra Pradesh). In Andhra Pradesh, Anantapuramu district was selected for the study as it has the highest area of 0.5 lakh ha with production of 10.96 lakh tonnes of sweet oranges. (Directorate of Economics and Statistics, 2021-22). In Anantapuramu district, according to the data obtained from Department of Horticulture, Anantapuramu; out of sixty-nine mandals, three mandals with a maximum area under sweet orange cultivation were selected purposively, which included Putluru, Yellanur, Narpala. Three villages from each mandal were selected, based on the highest area under sweet orange production. Komatikuntla, Venagannapalli, Putluru villages from Putluru mandal; Vennapusapalli, Nitturu, Venkatampalli villages from Yellanur; Narpala, Ganganapalli, B. Poppuru villages from Narpala mandal were selected. From each village seven participants and 13 non-participants were selected. A total of 63 participants and 117 non-participants participating in retail marketing were selected. The following tool was used for analysing the data collected.

Results and Discussion**Farming experience of farmers**

Usually, farmers can evolve from conventional agricultural methods to improved agricultural technologies as they gain experience through time by observing, taking part in various training programs, and

learning by doing. But in this study, it is observed that highly experienced farmers do not tend to change the way they market the produce, and do not wish to take risks. Less experienced or the farmers newly started sweet orange cultivation tend to adopt new and better marketing channels. Table 0.1 showed that majority of the participants were less than ten years' experience (69.84 per cent).

Farmers with experience greater than twenty years were majorly non-participants (30.77 per cent). It can be observed that 57.26 per cent and 19.05 per cent of the non-participants and participants had 11-20 years of experience in farming respectively. 43.89 per cent of the total respondents had experience between 11-20 years.

Table 0.1 Farming experience of farmers

Farming Experience (Years)	Participants (n=63)		Non-participants (n=117)		Total (n=180)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 10	44	69.84	14	11.97	58	32.22
11 to 20	12	19.05	67	57.26	79	43.89
Greater than 20	7	11.11	36	30.77	43	23.89
Total	63	100	117	100	180	100

Gender of the respondents

As expected in nations with strong patriarchal traditions, it was discovered that the gender distribution in both participant and non-participant categories leaned more towards the male sex than the female counterpart. Table 0.2 presents evidence to the above

statement in the form of percentage of male respondents at 85.71 and 86.32 per cent and female respondents at 14.29 and 13.68 per cent for participants and non-participants respectively. For total respondents, the per cent of male and female were found to be 86.11 and 13.89 per cent respectively.

Table 0.2 Gender of respondents

Gender	Participants (n=63)		Non-participants (n=117)		Total (n=180)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Male	54	85.71	101	86.32	155	86.11
Female	9	14.29	16	13.68	25	13.89
Total	63	100	117	100	180	100

Educational status of the farmer

The literacy rate of a population is one of the most important indicators of its socioeconomic development. When it comes to adopting new technologies and modern marketing methods, literacy plays critical role. The findings of the respondents' education status were shown in Table 0.3. The majority of the participant sample respondents (79.37 per cent) were educated, remaining participant sample respondents (20.63 per cent) were uneducated. The majority

of the non-participants were also educated (60.68 per cent) and 39.32 per cent were uneducated. A total of 67.22 per cent respondents were educated and 32.78 per cent respondents were uneducated. From these results, it can be inferred that the literacy rate was high among the participants than that of non-participants. As understanding retail marketing requires knowledge, more educated respondents participated in retail marketing.

Table 0.3 Educational status of the farmer

Education	Participants (n=63)		Non-participants (n=117)		Total (n=180)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Educated	50	79.37	71	60.68	121	67.22
Uneducated	13	20.63	46	39.32	59	32.78
Total	63	100	117	100	180	100

Land holding Particulars of Respondents

It could be observed from Table 0.4 that majority of the participants were semi-medium (46.03 per cent) and medium farmers (46.03 per cent), followed by small farmers (6.35 per cent) and large farmers (1.59 per cent). Majority of non-participants were small farmers (40.17 per cent) followed by semi-medium farmers (35.04 per cent), marginal farmers (19.66 per cent) and medium farmers (5.13 per

cent). Average size of land holding was found to be 4.36 and 1.86 hectares in case of participant and non-participant respondents respectively. Out of the total respondent's majority of the farmers were semi-medium farmers (38.89 per cent) and the least were large farmers (0.56 per cent). It can be inferred that the farmers having large farm size were more inclined to participate in retail marketing, than the farmers with less land holding.

Table 0.4 Land holding Particulars of Respondents

Farm size (in ha)	Participants (n=63)		Non-participants (n=117)		Total (n=180)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Marginal (less than 1 ha)	0	0	23	19.66	23	12.78
Small (1-2 ha)	4	6.35	47	40.17	51	28.33
Semi-medium (2-4 ha)	29	46.03	41	35.04	70	38.89
Medium (4-10 ha)	29	46.03	6	5.13	35	19.44
Large (greater than 10 ha)	1	1.59	0	0	1	0.56
Total	63	100	117	100	180	100
Average landholding (ha)	4.36		1.86		2.74	

Average annual income per hectare of the respondents

The average annual income of sample respondents is a significant economic indicator that influences the standard of living. The sample respondent's average annual income was presented in

Table.05. Average annual income of the total participants was Rs. 736523.81, total non-participants average annual income was Rs. 582576.92 and average annual income of the total sample respondents was Rs. 636458.33. Majority of the participants

belonged to the income range 7 to 7.5 lakhs (53.97 per cent) followed by income range more than 7.5 lakhs (28.57 per cent), 6.5 to 7 lakh (15.87 per cent) and 6 to 6.5 lakh (1.59 per cent). Majority of the non-participants belonged to the income range less than 5.5 lakhs (36.75

per cent) followed by income range 5.5 to 6 lakhs (29.91 per cent), 6 to 6.5 lakh (28.21 per cent) and 6.5 to 7 lakh (5.13 per cent). Farmers participating in retail marketing were getting higher level of income compared to non-participant respondents.

Table.5 Average annual income per hectare of respondents

Annual Income (Rs)	Participants (n=63)		Non-participants (n=117)		Total (n=180)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
<550000	0	0	43	36.75	43	23.89
550000-600000	0	0	35	29.91	35	19.44
600000-650000	1	1.59	33	28.21	34	18.89
650000-700000	10	15.87	6	5.13	16	8.89
700000-750000	34	53.97	0	0	34	18.89
>750000	18	28.57	0	0	18	10
Total	63	100	117	100	180	100
Average Annual Income (Rs)	736523.81		582576.92		636458.33	

Conclusion

Majority of the respondents (43.89 per cent) had an experience between 11 to 20 years. Majority of the participants i.e., 69.84 per cent had experience less than 10 years. Likewise, majority of the non-participants i.e., 57.26 per cent had experience between 11 to 20 years. Further, Male farmers formed a major part in the sample respondents (86.11 per cent). For participants and non-participants, the male farmers contribution was 85.71 and 86.32 per cent respectively. Among education status, most of the respondents were literate (67.22 per cent). About 79.37 per cent of the participants were literate and 60.68 per cent of the non-participants were literate. On Land holding status, the findings shows that, the Semi-medium farmers were the majority of the respondents (38.89 per cent). In the participants group majority were semi-medium (46.03 per cent) and medium (46.03 per cent) farmers. In the non-participants group majority were small (40.17 per cent) farmers. On income side, Majority of the respondents i.e., 23.89 per cent were getting income less than Rs. 550000. Most of the participants were getting more income than the non-participants. Also, the majority of the participants (53.97 per cent) got income between Rs. 700000 to Rs. 750000, the majority of the non-participants (36.75 per cent) got income less than Rs. 550000.

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